

The Totonacapan Culture-Religion

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The Totonac culture primarily developed between 600 and 1200 AD, with significant settlements also recorded during the Late Postclassic period (1200-1521 AD). The Totonacapan region corresponds specifically to the present-day Mexican state of Veracruz and parts of Puebla and Hidalgo. Its peak occurred mainly between 600 and 1200 AD, although it persisted beyond that period. The Totonac culture is renowned for its architectural achievements, sculptures, and popular rituals such as the 'Voladores de Papantla'.

Date Range: 600 CE - 1521 CE

Region: The Totonacapan region

Region tags: Latin America and the Caribbean, Mexico, Totonacapan Region, Mesoamerica

The Totonac culture developed in the present-day states of North Veracruz, Puebla, and Hidalgo. During the Classic and Epiclassic periods (600-1100 AD). The boundaries identified by the researchers correspond to the Cazonces River to the north, the Antigua River to the south, the Gulf of Mexico to the east, and the watershed of the mountain range to the west. This region was dominated by important centers like El Tajin. Then, during the Postclassic period, towns such as Cempoala.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: During the peak of El Tajín's splendor, the Totonacapan region had contact with Teotihuacan. Subsequently, during the Postclassic period, it maintained contact with Nahua groups, such as the Mexicas. This information is documented in the *Codex Mendoza* (1992) or *Diego Durán's chronicle* (2006), where it is mentioned that Cuetlaxtla, Cempoala, and Quihuiztlan sent gifts and tribute payments to Tenochtitlan.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– I don't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Totonacapan region encompasses urban and religious centers separated by clear social and geographical boundaries. Larger centers like El Tajín have been estimated to have a population ranging from 5,000 to 20,000 people (Koontz 2011: 53; Ladrón de Guevara 2010). Additionally, during the Postclassic period, centers like Cempoala reached populations of up to 30,000 inhabitants. These figures make it impossible to estimate the population of the entire region

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the exact population count is unknown, it is possible that the inhabitants of each city practiced the same worship. As mentioned, in larger cities, the population is estimated to be around

15,000 to 30,000 people.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Totonac group is united by speaking the same language. In sculptures and bas-reliefs, symbols can be identified that allude to representations of characters, gods, or mythical moments.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Totonac script appears in the form of glyphs on structures, monuments, and sculptures. Additionally, it corresponds to a living language with contemporary speakers. However, the full understanding of these glyphs and their relationship with the spoken language remains an ongoing area of study (Melgarejo Vivanco 1985).

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Field doesn't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: In most of the sites found, structures made of stone with stucco coatings are represented. In the case of central Mexico, large earth mounds have been located.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The most well-known information corresponds to El Tajín, where the surface area of the site corresponds to 1,067.728 hectares, of which around 190 to 240 have been excavated, corresponding to monumental, religious, and residential buildings (Olmos 2009; López Austin & López Luján 2001: 192).

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1296

Notes: The most important monument for this period is the Niches Pyramid located at the Tajin Site. Another significant characteristic is that it features 365 niches on its surface.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 18

Notes: The pyramid of the niches, in the Tajin, is the highest monument in the region

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 80

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: In sites like El Tajin, Cempoala, and Las Higueras, tombs have been discovered, typically rectangular, although some are circular. Inside, the remains of what have been interpreted as individuals of high social status have been found.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: One of the clearest pieces of evidence is observed at the Quiahuiztlán site, in central Veracruz. It is characterized by the tombs located on rectangular terraces.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The architecture excavated in this region varies in shapes, sizes, and the type of material they were built with. Generally, they correspond to stepped pyramid bases, which in some cases still preserve reliefs, remnants of murals, or sculptures depicting gods, human forms, or animals.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Notes: The reliefs and sculptures depict children, sacrifices, gods, mythical scenes, primarily located in religious centers. The most interesting case is the reliefs found at El Tajín, which are attached to the temples and palaces.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The most prominent features are the sharp and geometric shapes of the symbols, straight lines, and motifs forming fretwork, "star eyes," as well as representations of human figures, plants, and animals. These elements reflect the technical precision and rich symbolism of the Totonac culture.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– I don't know

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: There are different beliefs where the body separates from the soul at the moment of death, just as the soul can take the form of plants or animals.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The most well-known and studied reliefs in El Tajín depict gods, heroes, and supernatural beings such as the creation of the world, the struggle between deities, and the interaction between humans and gods. These scenes are richly detailed, with figures in dynamic poses and elaborate facial expressions that convey the intensity of the mythical narrative.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: In many cases, burials include funerary objects such as pottery, stone tools, items of personal adornment, and possibly ritual offerings.

Valuable items:

– Yes

Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– I don't know

Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Other valuable/precious items interred:

– I don't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Red pigment residues covering the body have been located, which was an important practice in pre-Hispanic times, as well as musical instruments.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Pre-Hispanic cemeteries have been discovered at various archaeological sites throughout the region, located both within religious centers and on the outskirts. These cemeteries served as burial places, apparently for local residents. Additionally, there were also ceremonial cemeteries dedicated to ritual and religious purposes. The best-studied case corresponds to the site of Quiahuiztlan. Interestingly, there is no evidence of a space with these characteristics in El Tajín.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Yes
Notes: Tláloc is depicted as a being with aquatic attributes and a bearer of rain. Quetzalcóatl is a deity represented as a feathered serpent. Ehécatl is the god of wind. All seem to be depicted in the friezes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– I don't know
Notes: There are representations of turtles that allude to the symbolism of the earth. Turtles are often associated with the earth and water and can be considered symbols of fertility and longevity. However, it is not possible to identify them with a specific character or goddess.
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: In several sites across Mesoamerica, rulers of these societies were often seen as intermediaries between the earthly and spiritual realms.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– No
Notes: The gods of the Mesoamerican pantheon are generally complex and multifaceted beings. They can be associated with fertility, sustenance, but also with war, droughts, death, and natural disasters.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– Yes [specify]: They are creator, regenerative deities, representing cosmic duality

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: They are the creators of the universe and enable the movement and maintenance of cosmic order. In the Totonac imagination, they are believed to control the entire world

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Yes

Notes: The gods are fed with offerings, the most important of which are sacrifices and self-sacrifices, as blood is the vital and most precious liquid. The gods must be fed to maintain their strength and uphold cosmic order.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

Notes: Adoration of main gods, natural guardian spirits dwelling in rivers, caves, or mountains, as well as animals appearing as actors in supernatural worlds, such as the jaguar, the eagle, and even insects, was allowed.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: They believed that ceremonial rituals and sacrifices were ways to communicate with the gods and gain their favor. Humans offered sacrifices as offerings to attract divine attention and obtain blessings or protection.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The gods were the creators of the universe, around whom several myths and beliefs developed, one of which has been spread throughout Mesoamerica, the myth of Quetzalcoatl, who was expelled from Tula, and his return was prophesied to mark the beginning of a new era. It is possible that these mythic passages were part of the beliefs among the ancient Totonacs. In Totonac culture, they believed in the existence of an underworld and an afterlife, where one's destiny depended on the

circumstances of their death. For example, women who died in childbirth were considered as warriors and acquired these attributes in the afterlife.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Yes

↳ Commoners:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Elites:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

↳ Elites:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– I don't know

↳ To out-groups:
– I don't know

↳ Destroyed:
– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: During ritual ceremonies such as the New Fire Festival, people gather in public squares.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that there were different professions depending on sex

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's possible. There were different contacts with the urban center of Teotihuacán during the Classic period. Later it is thought that several migrated to urban centers such as El Tajín. During the Postclassic period, the Totonacs interacted directly with cultures from central Mexico, particularly with the Mexica culture.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible, various investigations mention that during the Postclassic period different urban centers had areas for food storage.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Different representations in the reliefs of El Tajin show warriors and scenes of prisoners of war, however it has not been proven if the army was a particular institution.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During the Late Postclassic period, it has been proposed that the Mexica army corresponded to an independent institution, to which during the wars of conquest, neighboring peoples or peoples controlled by the empire came, such is the case of the peoples of the Gulf coast such as Cuetlaxtla, Cempoala or Huatusco.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: It's mainly known for pictorial elements, meaning the use of images and symbols to convey ideas or thoughts. They are placed on surfaces like ceramics, stone, or on the walls of buildings.

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Mesoamerican cities, they had a 365-day calendar and possibly a 260-day ritual. They

were used to organize agricultural activities, religious ceremonies, social events, and important rituals.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Cannibalism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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